

Surface Chemistry and Nano-/Microstructure Engineering on Photocatalytic In₂S₃ Nanocrystals

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KEYWORDS. Surface chemistry, aerogel, xerogel, In₂S₃, dye degradation, photocatalytic activity.

ABSTRACT: Colloidal nanocrystals (NCs) compete with molecular catalysts in the field of homogenous catalysis, offering an easier recyclability and a number of additional functionalities. Using high throughput printing technologies, colloidal NCs can be also supported onto substrates to produce cost-effective electronic, optoelectronic, electrocatalytic and sensing devices. In these

two broad areas, NCs surface chemistry and supracrystal organization are key parameters determining final performance. Here, we study the influence of the surface ligands and the NC organization on the catalytic properties of In_2S_3 , both in colloidal form and as a supported layer. In solution, well dispersed NCs stabilized in solution by inorganic ligands show the highest photocatalytic activities. On the other hand, when NCs are supported on a substrate, their organization becomes an essential parameters determining performance, and NC-based films produced through a gelation process provided five-fold higher photocurrent densities than those obtained from dense films produced by the direct printing of NCs.

INTRODUCTION

Semiconductor nanocrystals (NCs) combine huge surface areas with a solid state platform for charge carrier photogeneration and transport.¹ This combination of properties makes them particularly appealing for applications involving interaction with the media, such as catalysis,^{2,3} environmental remediation,^{4,5} and sensing.⁶ Colloidal NCs are especially suited for quasi-homogenous catalysis, where compared to molecular catalysts, they offer easier recyclability and added functionalities, such as magnetic moment for remote location or recovery, tunable band gaps for photocatalysis, and modulability to produce multisite systems by combining multiple co-catalysts.^{7,8} However, the ability of colloidal NCs to interact with the media is controlled by their surface chemistry, which also determines several other fundamental properties, including colloidal and chemical stabilities and charge carrier and surface trap densities.⁹ To find surface chemistries that simultaneously optimize all these parameters is extremely challenging and at the same time key to exploit their full potential.

Colloidal NCs can be also assembled or supported within macroscopic structures and devices as those required in electrocatalysis or sensing for instance.¹⁰⁻¹² Beyond their huge surface area,

solution processability and its related cost-effectiveness are main advantages of colloidal NCs in these fields, especially when compared with thin films produced by vacuum-based technologies. When supported, a proper NC organization becomes essential to maintain their inherent large surface areas, while at the same time ensuring proper electrical conductivities for effective charge injection/extraction.¹³ To face this key challenge, a plethora of approaches to engineer NC solids with controlled NC arrangement have been developed. A highly used approach involves a slow NC assembly driven by an oversaturation of the NC concentration during solvent removal.^{14,15} While yielding in some cases resulting astonishing NC assemblies, this strategy does not generally provide materials with large surface area and is strongly limited in terms of reproducibility, production throughput and scale up potential. To produce highly porous structures in a cost-effective manner, faster assembly strategies, based on destabilizing the NC dispersion in solution, are more suitable. This destabilization can be induced by externally triggering the ligand desorption or stimulating its binding. The ultimate goal is to produce an interconnected NC network, i.e. a gel, with a proper surface chemistry to interact with the media.¹⁶ In this direction, an effective approach to produce highly porous NC superstructures is the oxidative removal of thiolate ligands to link chalcogenide NCs through chalcogen-chalcogen bonds.¹⁷ Following this approach, gels of several chalcogenides have been produced.¹⁸⁻²⁰

In_2S_3 is an n-type semiconductor with a 2.6 eV band gap. In_2S_3 NCs has been used in lithium-ion batteries,²¹ photodetector,²² for solar energy conversion through photocatalysis,²³⁻²⁵ and particularly as a host material for two-photon absorption processes through an intermediate band.^{26,27} While its chemical stability, low defect density, simple synthesis, and proper band gap makes it an excellent candidate for photocatalytic applications, this material has been underexplored in this area. In this work, we evaluate the photocatalytic activity of colloidal In_2S_3

NCs both in solution and when supported. We analyze the effect of different surface chemistries and NC organizations to determine the conditions resulting in best performances.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Materials. Indium trichloride (InCl_3 , 98%), oleylamine (OAm, 70%), oleic acid (OAc, 90%), sulfur powder (99.998 %), 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA, 95%), tetramethylammonium hydroxide pentahydrate (TMOH, $\geq 97\%$), dodecanethiol (DDT, $\geq 98\%$), tert-dodecanethiol (tDDT, 98.5 %), N-methylformamide (MFA, 99 %), phosphotungstic acid hydrate ($\text{H}_3[\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, PhTA, 95 %), trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, 99 %), tetranitromethane (TNM, 95 %), rhodamine B (RhB, 97 %), sodium hydroxide (NaOH, $\geq 98\%$), sodium sulfide (Na_2S), potassium chloride (KCl , $\geq 99\%$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Hexane, methanol and acetone were of analytical grade and were purchased from Panreac. Glass substrates coated with indium tin oxide (ITO, $\sim 8 \Omega/\text{sq}$) were acquired from VWR. All syntheses were carried out using standard air-free Schlenk-line techniques.

Synthesis of In_2S_3 NCs. Among the several established synthetic protocols to produce In_2S_3 NCs with different shapes and sizes,^{21-22,25,28} we followed a slight variation of the procedure reported by Park et al.,²⁸ to obtain In_2S_3 NCs with a two-dimensional morphology. In a 25 mL flask three-neck flask, 1 mmol of InCl_3 and 10 mL of OAm were mixed and degassed (~ 100 mTors) for 60 minutes at 80 °C under magnetic stirring. During this time, a clear solution formed. Then, temperature was raised up to 220 °C (5 °C/min) and, at this temperature, a previously degassed (15 minutes) solution containing 1.5 mmol of sulphur powder in 5 mL of OAm was swiftly injected. Upon injection of the sulphur precursor, the color of the solution gradually changed from transparent to orange, indicating the NC formation. After 10 minutes,

the reaction was quenched by removing the heating mantle and placing the flask in a water bath. During the cooling step, the color of the solution changed from orange to yellow. Once at room temperature, NCs were precipitated by adding 30 mL of acetone to the crude solution and centrifuging the mixture at 5700 rpm for 5 min. The supernatant was discarded and the precipitate was re-dispersed in 5 mL of hexane. A second purification step was performed following the same procedure. Finally, NCs dispersed in 5 mL of hexane were stored for posterior use.

Surface modification with $(PW_{12}O_{40})^{3+}$:²⁹ 1 mL of a 10 mg/mL dispersion of In_2S_3 NCs in hexane was mixed with 1 mL of a MFA solution that contained 20 mL of TFA and 50 mg of PhTA, forming a biphasic solution. This solution was vigorously shaken for 10 seconds and stirred 30-60 minutes. After stirring, the mixture was allowed to separate in two phases. The migration of NCs from the upper hexane phase to the lower MFA phase indicated the success in the ligand exchange. The upper liquid phase was discarded and then 2 mL of a hexane: acetone (1:1) mixture was added to the vial. The solution was then shaken and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 min. This step was repeated 3 times to remove the former un-bonded ligands. Finally, the precipitated NCs were redispersed in MQ-Water for dye degradation measurements and in methanol for film preparation.

Surface modification with $InCl_3$:³⁰ The same procedure detailed above to modify the In_2S_3 NCs surface with PhTA was used to modify them with $InCl_3$, with two small differences: i) the 1 mL MFA solution contained 30 mg of $InCl_3$ (not 50 mg); ii) to facilitate the phase transfer / ligand exchange, instead of TFA, 1 mL of acetone was additionally introduced in the initial biphasic solution before shaking.

Surface modification with MUA:³¹ 5 mL of a 20 mg/mL dispersion of In_2S_3 NCs were mixed with 5 mL of a MUA solution (2 mM in methanol). The resulting biphasic solution was stirred under inert atmosphere for 30 min. During this time, NCs moved from the upper hexane phase to the bottom methanol phase. Then, the upper part was removed and NCs were precipitated by addition of 30 mL of acetone and centrifuging at 4000 rpm for 5 min. The obtained precipitate was redispersed in methanol and precipitated one more time with acetone. It should be noted that repeating the washing procedure led to NCs aggregation but addition of MUA redispersed NCs back in solution.

Direct NC deposition: 1 mL of the hexane or methanol solution containing In_2S_3 NCs (20 mg/mL) with the selected surface ligand (OAm, $(\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})^{3-}$, InCl, MUA) was spin-coated on previously washed ITO substrates at a rotation speed of 2000 rpm for 20 seconds. The obtained films were annealed at 250 °C for 60 min under argon flow.

NC deposition through xerogel formation: 1 mL of MUA-capped In_2S_3 NCs (20 mg/mL) in methanol was spin-coated on ITO substrates at a rotation speed of 2000 rpm for 20 seconds. Immediately after preparation, the film was dipped in a TNM solution (50 μL of 3% TNM in 5 mL of acetone) for 1 min. Subsequently, the film was rinsed with fresh methanol to remove by-products and then annealed at 250 °C for 60 min under argon flow.

Gel and aerogel preparation:¹⁹ To produce In_2S_3 NC gels, 50 μL of a TNM solution (3% in acetone) were added into 2 mL of a methanol solution containing MUA-capped In_2S_3 NCs (10 mg/mL). The mixture was shaken vigorously for 30 seconds and kept undisturbed for the whole gelation process. The gelation process visually evolved during 2 h, but we left the solution undisturbed for two days to ensure its completion. After two days, the solvent mixture (methanol and acetone) was exchanged to pure acetone, removing all the methanol and TNM residues. This

process must be carried out with especial care in order not to damage the porous network of the gel. At the same time, the solvent cannot be completely removed at any step. Thus, we partially replaced the solvent every 1-2 h for 2 days. While not optimized, relatively long time intervals between solvent replacements were used to ensure complete penetration of the fresh solvent into the porous structure of the wet gel. After the solvent exchange, the gel immersed in acetone was loaded into a supercritical point dryer chamber. Then, the chamber was loaded with liquid CO₂ and kept overnight. After 12 h, the chamber was half drained and filled with fresh liquid CO₂. This procedure was repeated for at least 6 times in one-hour intervals in order to replace all the acetone with liquid CO₂. Finally, the chamber was completely filled with liquid CO₂ and heated to 39 °C. Upon heating, the pressure increased up to 75-80 bars, thus overpassing the supercritical point of CO₂. The sample was kept under these conditions for 1 h. Afterward, the pressure was released while keeping the temperature constant.

Dye degradation experiments: The photocatalytic activity of In₂S₃ NCs was evaluated by photodegradation of RhB. In a typical experiment, 1 mL of an aqueous RhB solution (100 ppm) was added to 9 mL of an aqueous solution containing In₂S₃ NCs (1.1 mg/mL). Before reaction, the mixture was kept in the dark for 30 min under magnetic stirring. Then the glass reaction vessel was exposed through its open top to the light from a 300 W xenon lamp providing ca. 100 mW/cm² irradiance at the sample. Irradiation was maintained for 2 h.

Photoelectrochemical measurements: The photoelectrocatalytic activity of In₂S₃ NCs was evaluated through the photoelectrochemical oxidation of a polysulfide electrolyte:³²

being the oxidized species, S_x²⁻, converted back (reduced) to S²⁻ on the counter electrode:

Photocurrent measurements were performed using a three-electrode cell configuration with a Pt-coiled wire having a surface area of 2 cm² as a counter electrode and an Ag/AgCl reference electrode filled with 3M KCl solution. 1M aqueous solution of S, NaOH and Na₂S at pH7 was used as an electrolyte. Bias voltage to the working electrode was applied through an electrical contact to the uncoated part of the ITO-glass substrate. A surface area of 1 cm² of the deposited film was in contact with the electrolyte. Illumination was provided by 8 xenon lamps (35 W each) radially distributed with a total power of 280 W and irradiance on the sample of ca. 100 mW/cm².

Characterization techniques. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) characterization was carried out using a ZEISS LIBRA 120, operating at 120 kV. Samples were prepared by drop casting a diluted NC solution onto a carbon coated copper grid (200 mesh). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis was carried out using a ZEISS Auriga microscope. For SEM characterization, NCs were dispersed in appropriate solvent and drop casted onto silicon substrates. X-ray power diffraction (XRD) analyses were carried out on a Bruker AXS D8 ADVANCE X-ray diffractometer with Ni-filtered (2 μm thickness) Cu Kα1 radiation (λ = 1.5406 Å). For XRD analysis, NCs in solution were drop casted (200-500 μL at a concentration of about 3 mg/mL) onto a zero-signal silicon wafer. UV-vis absorption spectra were recorded on a PerkinElmer LAMBDA 950 UV-vis spectrophotometer. Samples were prepared by diluting 100 μL in 2 mL of hexane inside a 10 mm path length quartz cuvette. UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectra were acquired with a Jasco V-570 UV/Vis/NIR spectrophotometer equipped with an integrating sphere. The solid sample was placed on the sample holder and measured from 1000 to 300 nm and the baseline was corrected using a BaSO₄ reflectance standard. The Kubelka-Munk equation was employed to convert reflectance to absorption.³³ FTIR spectra were recorded

form 500 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} using a PerkinElmer FT-IR 2000 spectrophotometer. Dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements were performed using a Zeta Sizer (Malvern Instruments) equipped with a 4.0 mW HeNe laser operating at 633 nm and an avalanche photodiode detector. For DLS analysis, samples were diluted in 2 mL of appropriate solvent inside a 10 mm path length glass cuvette. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were carried out on a SPECS system equipped with an Al anode XR50 source operating at 150 mW and a Phoibos 150 MCD-9 detector.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1a displays a representative TEM micrograph of the $18 \pm 2\text{ nm}$ In_2S_3 NCs produced through the injection of a OAm-sulfur solution into a hot ($220\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) OAm solution containing InCl_3 , as described in the experimental section. Using this synthetic protocol, In_2S_3 NCs with disk-like morphology were produced. Their size could be adjusted in the range from 18 nm to 90 nm by changing the surfactant type and concentration, the amount of sulfur precursor and the reaction time (see details in the supporting information, SI, Figure S1).

Figure 1. a-d) Representative TEM micrographs and corresponding DLS spectra of the initial In₂S₃ NCs (a) and of the In₂S₃ NCs capped with MUA (b), (PW₁₂O₄₀)³⁻ (c), and InCl (d). All micrographs have the same scale bar = 50 nm. e) Z-potential measurements of the In₂S₃ NCs capped with MUA, (PW₁₂O₄₀)³⁻, and InCl. e) TGA profiles of the initial In₂S₃ NCs (OAm-NCs) and of the In₂S₃ NCs capped with MUA and (PW₁₂O₄₀)³⁻.

The presence of OAm in the reaction mixture was fundamental to produce In₂S₃ crystals with sizes in the nanometer size regime and with narrow size and shape distributions. OAm binds indium ions at the NCs surface, limiting the access/reaction of additional monomer and thus confining the NC growth. At the same time, OAm molecules bind at the NC surface colloiddally stabilize them during synthesis, enabling their homogeneous growth. While OAm is fundamental

to control NCs growth, it remained at the NC surface after initial purification steps, as observed by FTIR analysis (Figure 1g), what potentially limited their surface chemical activity.

To determine the effect of surface ligands on the photocatalytic properties of In_2S_3 NCs and to direct their assembly, OAm was replaced with three different ligands: $(\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})^{3-}$, InCl and MUA. In all cases, new ligands were introduced using convenient two-phase solution methods previously reported and adapted to our system.^{29,30}

In brief, to replace the native OAm with inorganic ligands, a hexane solution containing the In_2S_3 NCs was mixed with a MFA/TFA solution of PhTA or with a MFA solution of InCl_3 . This process rendered the NCs soluble in polar media such as methanol or H_2O , as confirmed by TEM and DLS measurements (Figure 1 c, d).

XPS measurements corroborated the presence of $(\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})^{3-}$ and InCl on the surface of In_2S_3 NCs. XPS measurements of the In_2S_3 NCs stabilized with $(\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})^{3-}$ ($(\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})^{3-}$ -NCs) demonstrated the presence of tungsten at the In_2S_3 NC surface ($\sim 1\%$) with a main oxidation state compatible with that of a tungstate (W 4f7/2 binding energy = 35.8 eV, Figure 2a).³⁴ In_2S_3 NCs stabilized with InCl (InCl-NCs) displayed an excess of In (In/S = 1.0) and the presence of Cl ($\sim 3\%$) with a chemical environment compatible with that of InCl (Cl 1s binding energy = 445.2 eV, Figure 2b).³⁴

OAm was replaced with MUA by mixing In_2S_3 NCs in hexane with a MUA solution in methanol.¹⁶ This process rendered the In_2S_3 NCs soluble in polar media such as methanol, isopropanol or water (Figure 2c). FTIR spectra of In_2S_3 NCs stabilized with MUA (MUA-NCs) showed the presence of the peaks at 2924 cm^{-1} and 2830 cm^{-1} that correspond to C-H stretching (Figure 1 g). However, due to the shorter chain length of MUA compared with OAm, the intensity of these peaks was lower than in the initial OAm-stabilized In_2S_3 NCs (OAm-NCs).

The disappearance of the weak peak at 2547 cm^{-1} present in the spectrum of pure MUA and which was attributed to the S-H stretching, evidenced the binding of the ligand to the metal atom through the thiol group. Finally, the peaks at 1547 cm^{-1} and 1406 cm^{-1} observed in the FTIR spectrum of the MUA-NCs are attributed to the asymmetric and symmetric vibration band of the carboxylate, respectively, proving the presence of this functional group.

Figure 2. a) XPS spectrum of the In 3d, S 2p and Cl 1s regions obtained from $(PW_{12}O_{40})^{3-}$ -NCs. a) XPS spectrum of the In 3d, S 2p and Cl 1s regions obtained from InCl-NCs. c) FTIR spectra of OAm and MUA; MUA-NCs dispersed in methanol and OAm-NCs in hexane; and a NC aerogel.

MUA-NCs were used as building blocks to produce sulfide gels. The assembly of MUA-NCs was triggered by exposing them to TNM (3% TNM solution in methanol), a non-oxygen-transferring oxidant.³⁵ As previously described,¹⁷ TNM oxidizes the thiolate ligands bond to In^{3+} ions at the NC surface. The oxidized thiolate moves to solution probably in the form of disulfides. Upon thiolate displacement from the NC surface, In^{3+} ions at the NC surface can be easily solvated by the carboxylate species or methanol, leaving a chalcogen rich NC surface. In

such chalcogen-rich NCs, and in the presence of additional amounts of the oxidizer, a chalcogen catenation takes place, resulting in the aggregation of the NCs into a network held together by interparticle chalcogen–chalcogen binding.¹⁷ This aggregation mechanism allows to directly interconnect adjacent NCs, without mediating any ligand that could hinder, for instance, interparticle charge transfer.

The formed gel was subsequently dried under super-critical CO₂ to retain the porous structure (Figure 3b, 3c). TEM image of the resulting aerogel (Figure 3b, inset) revealed the fusing of the NCs into chains with diameters of around 20 nm which is consistent with the size of the initial NCs. HRTEM images confirmed that aerogel formation occurred through the coalescence of randomly oriented NCs (Figure S3). SEM characterization of aerogels displayed the highly porous three dimensional structure with large voids (Figure 3c). FTIR analysis of the final aerogel evidenced that the gelation process was accompanied by the removal of MUA as proven by the suppression of the 2800-2900 cm⁻¹ peak corresponding to the C-H vibration band (Figure 3g). The amount of oxidizing agent introduced was a key parameter controlling the gelation process. Too little amounts of TNM resulted in partial NC aggregation and precipitation but without the formation of a proper NC network. On the other hand, too large amounts of the oxidizing agent strongly accelerated the NC aggregation by efficiently removing all the MUA molecules and leading to extensive chalcogen-chalcogen bond formation. This high reactivity resulted in much denser gels (Figure S2).

Type IV nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms, characteristic of mesoporous structures, were observed from the NC aerogels (Figure 3d). From the fitting of the data to a Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) model,³⁶ the surface area of In₂S₃ NC aerogels was determined to be ca. 134 m²/g, while that of precipitated MUA-NCs was just 40 m²/g (Figure 3d).

Figure 3. a) Vials containing the MUA-NC solution in methanol, a NC wet gel, the supercritically dried NCs aerogel and the precipitated and dried MUA-NCs. b) TEM and c) SEM micrographs of an In_2S_3 NC aerogel. d) Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms of an In_2S_3 NC aerogel and of dried MUA-NCs. e) Scheme of the gel formation by oxidation of MUA and sulphur ions at the NC surface.

The photocatalytic performance of In_2S_3 NCs in suspension was evaluated through the degradation of RhB under a xenon lamp irradiation. In a typical measurement, 20 mg of NCs were suspended in 10 mL of water containing 10 ppm of RhB. Before irradiation, the solution was stirred in the dark for 30 min to achieve adsorption equilibrium. OAm-NCs were not stable in water, thus they were not tested for RhB degradation. MUA-NCs showed a poor activity toward photodegradation of RhB, reaching just 60% of RhB degradation after 2 h illumination (Figure 4). We associated this poor performance to the limited access of RhB to the MUA-covered NC surface and possibly also in part to the polymerization of MUA under illumination, which resulted in a progressive NC aggregation and consequent surface loss.³⁷⁻³⁹ $(\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})^{3-}$ and InCl-NCs provided the highest RhB degradation rates, which we attributed to the high

accessibility of their surface both due to the absence of organics and the fair stability of the NCs in solution (Figure 4). The In_2S_3 NC-gel showed intermediate efficiency for RhB degradation. NC-gels provided organic-free In_2S_3 surfaces but with lower total active areas compared with colloidal NCs.

Figure 4. Photocatalytic degradation curves of RhB on MUA-NCs, $(\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})^{3-}$ -NCs, InCl-NCs and the NC-gel.

To investigate their photoelectrocatalytic properties, In_2S_3 NCs were supported on ITO-covered glass substrates. NC layers were prepared by spin coating a methanol solution of the NCs (Figure 5). To produce porous films, the MUA-NC layer was dipped into a TNM solution immediately after spin coating, interconnecting in this way the In_2S_3 NCs into a porous network.¹⁹ The layer was afterwards rinsed with methanol to remove reaction by-products. All layers were annealed at 250 °C for 60 min under argon flow before photoelectrocatalytic characterization.

Figure 5. SEM images of films obtained by spin-coating OAm-NCs (a), MUA-NCs (b), $(PW_{12}O_{40})^{3-}$ -NCs (c) and InCl-NCs (d) and MUA-NCs which were posteriorly linked with TNM to produce a xerogel film (e) through the process schematized in (f). Scale bar=2 μ m.

The photoelectrocatalytic performance of In_2S_3 NCs was evaluated using a three-electrode cell with a Pt-coiled counter electrode, an Ag/AgCl reference electrode and the NCs film as working electrode. A polysulfide solution, consisting of a 1 M aqueous solution of Na_2S , NaOH and S, was used as electrolyte. Figure 6 shows the results obtained from linear sweep voltammograms and time-dependent photocurrent measurements of the different layers.

Films obtained by spin coating OAm- and MUA-NCs showed the lowest performance. We attribute this experimental observation to the limited access to the NC surface and to the low electrical conductivity of the film. The hydrophobic nature of the NCs capped with OAm may further reduce the OAm-NC interaction with the reaction solution further reducing the current

density. Considering its shorter hydrocarbon chain compared to OAm, MUA-NC films provided a better contact between the NCs and the electrolyte, leading to slightly higher photocurrent densities than OAm-NCs films. Layers produced from $(PW_{12}O_{40})^{3-}$ -NCs and InCl-NCs showed improved photocurrents compared with OAm-NCs, which we attributed to a more efficient charge transfer and transport with the media and between the NCs. However, xerogel films provided the highest photocurrent densities, reaching $150 \mu A/cm^2$ at $1.0 V$ vs Ag/AgCl (Figure 6a). We attributed the enhanced performance of the xerogel films to the absence of organic ligands hampering charge transfer and transport, to a close interconnection between NCs through the chalcogen-chalcogen bonds, which improved charge transport, and to a high layer porosity offering large active areas for interaction with the media.

Figure 6. Linear sweep voltammogram curves (a) and chronoamperometric characteristics normalized by the amount of photoactive material at $0.3 V$ vs. Ag/AgCl (b) of xerogel layers and layers produced from OAm-, MUA-, $(PW_{12}O_{40})^{3-}$ - and InCl-NCs. The total mass of the material onto substrate was determined by ICP measurements.

CONCLUSIONS

We compared the photocatalytic and photoelectrocatalytic performance of disk-shaped In_2S_3 NCs with different surface chemistries and supra-crystalline organization. Dispersions of In_2S_3 NCs, colloidally stabilized with inorganic ligands such as polyoxometallates or chlorides, showed the highest photocatalytic performance toward dye degradation in solution. We attributed this experimental fact to the higher accessibility of the NC surface provided by the inorganic ligands compared with the organic ones and to the colloidal stability of the materials, which provided maximized surface areas to interact with the media. On the other hand, organized NC assemblies provided higher photoelectrocatalytic performances than organic- and inorganic-capped NCs. The organization of the NCs into NC networks held together through chalcogen-chalcogen bonds simultaneously provided larger surface areas for interaction with the media compared with layers of precipitated NCs, and effective avenues for charge transport through the layer.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at DOI:

Additional experimental details. TEM images of In_2S_3 NCs with different sizes and shapes.

Optical photographs of In_2S_3 NC-gel obtained using different amount of TNM. HRTEM analysis. Band gap determination. Chronoamperometric characteristics obtained from NC-xerogel films with different thickness

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ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the European Regional Development Funds and the Spanish MINECO project BOOSTER. TB thanks FI-AGAUR Research Fellowship Program, Generalitat de Catalunya (2015 FI_B 00744). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 712949 (TECNIOspring PLUS) and the Government of Catalonia's Agency for Business Competitiveness (ACCIÓ).

ABBREVIATIONS

NC, nanocrystal; OAm, oleylamine; OAc, oleic acid; MUA, 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid; TMOH, tetramethylammonium hydroxide pentahydrate; DDT, dodecanethiol; tDDT, tert-dodecanethiol; MFA, n-methylformamide; PhTA, phosphotungstic acid hydrate; TFA, trifluoroacetic acid; TNM, tetranitromethane; RhB, rhodamine B; ITO, indium tin oxide; TEM, transmission electron microscopy; HRTEM, high-resolution TEM; SEM, scanning electron microscopy; UV-vis, ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy; UV/vis/NIR, ultraviolet-visible near infrared spectroscopy; X-ray power diffraction (XRD); DLS, dynamic light scattering; FTIR, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy; XPS, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy; ICP, inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy; OAm-NCs, OAm-capped NCs; (PW₁₂O₄₀)³⁻-NCs, (PW₁₂O₄₀)³⁻-capped NCs; InCl-NCs, InCl-capped NCs; MUA-NCs, MUA-capped NCs.

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